

Enhancing Edible Insect Protein Digestibility: Impact of Traditional Processing Techniques

Bhanita Bora

Research Scholar

Department of Zoology, Cotton University, Assam

The persistent increase in human population and diminishing agricultural output stand as major factors of inadequate protein diets in developing countries. Edible insects gained attention as food and feed ingredients as their sustainable and nutrient-rich protein sources. However, the nutritional content of edible insects becomes truly beneficial only when the proteins within them are effectively digestible. This study investigates the impact of traditional processing methods, specifically boiling and frying, on the *in vitro* protein digestibility of three edible insect species: *Cybister tripunctatus asiaticus*, *Chondracris rosea* and *Polistis oliyaceus*. The results indicated that boiling and frying elicited a significant enhancement in the protein content of all three chosen edible insect species when contrasted with their raw counterparts. The highest protein content was recorded in fried sample of *Cybister tripunctatus asiaticus* ($63.29 \pm 0.05\%$) and the lowest protein content was recorded in raw sample of *Macrotermes natalensis* ($33.40 \pm 0.04\%$). A significant variation in protein digestibility was observed between boiling and frying methods for three selected edible insects suggesting that the choice of processing method plays a crucial role in enhancing or diminishing the nutritional quality of these insects. The highest protein digestibility value was observed in boiled sample of *Cybister tripunctatus asiaticus* ($63.43 \pm 0.09\%$) whereas the lowest protein digestibility value was observed in fried sample of *Polistis oliyaceus* ($43.03 \pm 0.12\%$). The findings emphasize the importance of selecting appropriate processing methods to optimize the protein digestibility of edible insects, thereby promoting their sustainable utilization as an alternative protein source in the global food shortage.

Keywords: Edible insects; Processing; Protein digestibility; Nutritional content